

Mechanical studies, surface analysis, luminescence studies of an organic NLO material : 5-Nitroindole

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Abstract : Single crystal of 5-nitroindole was grown by slow cooling solution growth technique. Vicker's microhardness test has carried out in order to understand the mechanical properties of the grown crystal. The Meyer's index number shows the material belong to soft category. The crystal surface has analyzed by chemical etching and atomic force microscopy (AFM). The etching study reveals the growth pattern and dislocations present in the grown crystal. The amplitude parameters measured from AFM studies helps to analyze the surface topography of the grown crystal. The emission spectrum has recorded between 540–720 nm. The broad emission band appeared in the region 552–567 nm shows the blue emission in the crystal.

Keywords : Crystal growth, mechanical studies, surface analysis, luminescence.

Introduction

Nonlinear optical materials find a variety of applications including telecommunications, optical computing, optical data storage, and optical information processing. The interests in organic materials are due to their high nonlinearities, ultra fast response and high laser damage threshold¹. The advantages of organic materials are flexibility in the method of synthesis and scope for altering the properties by functional substitution. Hence new organic materials are in high demand to meet the several requirements. Organic π conjugated molecules having electron acceptor and donor group shows the large nonlinear property². The title compound 5-nitroindole (5NI) is a fused ring heterocyclic compound containing electron donors and acceptors are the potential candidate for NLO applications. The angle between the molecular charge transfer axis and polar axis angle of the 5-nitroindole crystal is 52.72° ³. The second harmonic generation efficiency of 5NI is 20 times greater than that of urea as reported by the standard Kurtz and Perry technique⁴. Investigation on the properties of the material helps to identify the suitable crystal for device applications. In this paper, for the first time, reporting the micro hardness properties, surface analysis and luminescence studies of 5NI single crystal.

Experimental

The commercially available 5-nitroindole ($C_8H_6N_2O_2$) obtained from Sigma-Aldrich 98% has used for the crystal growth. The saturated solution of 5NI was prepared at $35^\circ C$ using methanol as a solvent. The transparent and homogeneous solution was obtained by continuous stirring of the solution. The solution was filtered in a beaker using Whatmann filter paper and covered with a perforated lid. Then the beaker was housed in a constant temperature bath (CTB) and left for 1 day at same temperature. After 1 day, the temperature of CTB was reduced by $\pm 0.01^\circ C/day$. Good quality single crystal of 5NI was harvested from the mother solution after two weeks.

Results and discussion

Microhardness test :

Mechanical strength of the material plays a key role in the device fabrication. The mechanically flexible, non-destructive single crystal is of high demand in the application of organic electronics⁵. Vickers hardness is one of the important deciding factors in selecting the crystals for device applications. The crystal has to cross the various processing steps like cutting, grinding, polishing for the fabrication of devices. Microhardness test has carried out using an MH-112 Vickers microhardness tester (Japan) instrument. Indentation test has carried out on the (001)

plane by applying loads 10, 25, 50 and 100 g for a dwell time of 10 s. Vickers diamond pyramid indenter attached to the incident ray research microscope was used for the indentation purpose. The indented impressions were approximately square in shape. The calibrated micrometer attached to the eyepiece of the microscope helps to determine the average diagonal length of the indentation mark. After unloading, the average 'd' has found out. The Vickers microhardness number of the crystal H_v has calculated using the formula,

$$H_v = 1.8544 P/d^2 \quad (1)$$

where d is the mean diagonal length of the indentation in mm. P is the applied load in grams. H_v is the Vickers hardness number in kg/mm^2 . Beyond 100 g, the cracks were appeared on the crystal; hence hardness test was not carried out above this load.

The plot of H_v as a function of applied load is shown in Fig. 1. From the plot, it has observed that the hardness of the crystal was decreased up to 50 g, after which its

Fig. 1. Load vs H_v of 5NI.

value tends to achieve saturation. This behavior is termed as normal indentation size effect (ISE). The easiest way to describe the ISE is Meyers' law⁶. The relation between the load and indentation diagonal length was given as

$$P = kd^n \quad (2)$$

$$\log p = \log k + n \log d \quad (3)$$

where the exponent 'n' is a Meyer number and A is a constant. The graph between $\log p$ and $\log d$ is a straight line. The slope of the graph gives 'n' value as 1.01. Vickers hardness value should increase in H_v with increasing load for $n > 2$ and should decrease for $n < 2$. The 'n' value is in accord with the experimental values. According to Onitsch⁷ and Hanneman⁸, the 'n' value of hard material lies between 1 and 1.6 and above 1.6 shows a soft materials category. The value of 'n' shows the crystal belongs to the soft material.

Photoluminescence studies :

The PL spectrum was recorded using Jobin Yvon-Spex spectrofluorometer (Fluorolog version 3 : Model FL3-11). The high pressure xenon lamp operated at 450 W acts as an excitation source. The luminescence is due to the localized π -electron systems within individual organic molecules. The PL intensity is most probably dependent on the crystalline nature and structural perfection of the grown crystal. Fig. 2 shows the PL spectrum and molecular structure (inside image) of 5NI single crystal. The sample has excited at 529 nm. The emission spectrum has recorded between 540–720 nm. The broad emission band appeared in the region 552–567 nm shows the emission of blue radiation. The emission of blue radiation helps to find their applications in blue light emitting diodes.

Etching studies :

The chemical etching technique is the simplest technique to find the dislocations present in the grown crystal

Fig. 2. Photoluminescence spectrum of 5NI.

using an appropriate chemical reagent⁹. To investigate the perfection of the crystalline sample, etching studies have done using different solvent as an etchant at room temperature. Etch patterns have analyzed using a Carl Zeiss metallurgical micro-scope (Axioskop 40 MAT) in the reflection mode. The etching studies have carried out on the fresh cleavage surface (001) plane of a single crystal. In the perfect lattice, during etching reaction, activation energy is higher than etch rates of the complete lattice results in the formation of etch pits. The crystal surface without any etching has a smooth surface is shown in Fig. 3a. When the etching was carried out in methanol for 60 s, striation patterns were observed which is shown in Fig. 3b. Fig. 3c shows similar step like pattern when etched with water for 60 s. Fig. 3d shows small circular pits when ethyl acetate has used as an etchant. From the etching studies, it shows that the pits are due to variation in super saturation, growth rate and the strain formed during the crystal growth. It is found that the fast dissolving solvent produce better etch pits.

Fig. 3. (a) Without etching, (b) 60 s etching in methanol, (c) 60 s etching in water and (d) 60 s etching in ethyl acetate.

AFM studies :

The surface features of the grown crystal were investigated using Atomic force microscope (AFM). The study was carried out in the ambient atmosphere at room temperature. The AFM images were collected using Nanosurf scan 2 instrument in contact mode. The standard SiN

cantilever with a small force constant of 42/NM integrated with Nanoprobe tips can be used. Using the software (Nanosurf scan version 1-4-0-3), the parameters are roughness average, peak valley height, valley depth, root mean square, the mean value, have estimated. The obtained values are roughness average (S_a) = 25.84 nm, Root mean square (S_q) = 37.67 nm, Peak-valley height (S_v) = 336.1 nm, Peak height (S_p) = 173.9 nm, Valley depth (S_v) = -162.2 nm, Mean value (S_m) = -10.014 pm.

Conclusions

Single crystal of 5NI has grown by slow cooling solution growth method. Microhardness study shows that the hardness of the material decreases with increasing load reveals the indentation size effect. The photoluminescence spectrum appeared in the region 552–567 nm shows the emission of blue radiation. Etching study shows the presence of striations and step patterns are due to dislocations present in the crystal. The various amplitude parameters were measured from Atomic force microscopy. The obtained results from various characterizations shows that the crystal is an interesting material for second order nonlinear optical applications.

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